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Joint Priorities for International Collaboration on Standards

This document presents the jointly agreed priorities for international standards collaboration between INSTAR and TTA across six technology areas: AI, Cybersecurity/e-ID, Quantum, Cloud/Edge/IoT, 5G/6G, and Data.

It outlines the key work items jointly identified by INSTAR and TTA experts as common priorities for future Europe-Republic of Korea cooperation on standards development and international standardisation activities.

These priorities were identified through online exchanges and further discussed during the joint onsite workshop held in Seoul on 5 November 2025.

The document is intended to serve as a reference for planning joint contributions, technical cooperation, and future collaboration initiatives.

INSTAR

INSTAR is an EU-funded project that supports the future of ICT standardisation by connecting top European experts across emerging technology fields and collaborating with key entities from Canada, Japan, the Republic of Korea, and Singapore to develop strategic Priorities for International Cooperation on Standards (PICS).

TTA

The Telecommunications Technology Association (TTA) is an ICT standardisation and testing/certification organisation in the Republic of Korea. TTA develops and distributes ICT standards for emerging technologies such as AI, quantum, mobile communications, and security, while also providing testing and certification services for ICT products in line with domestic and international standards. It also promotes global cooperation to harmonise international standards, offers training programmes for standardisation and testing professionals, and supports the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises through technical support and infrastructure.

5G+/6G Standardisation Priorities

- **Networking Systems and Architectures**

Promote open, interoperable, secure, and energy-efficient infrastructures via the development of a joint white paper on global connectivity.

- **6G Radio**

Collaborate to develop one non-backward compatible radio access technology to meet a broad range of use cases, and requirements.

- **5G/6G AI-RAN**

Collaborate to develop specification support for CSI feedback enhancement use case as well as standards-based UE data collection.

Artificial Intelligence Standardisation Priorities

- **Risk management: testable methods**
Share methodologies for risk evaluation and lifecycle trust.
- **Dataset quality & provenance**
Exchange of risk-based dataset quality metrics; representativeness.
- **Human oversight patterns**
Exchange information on prescriptive oversight patterns (human-in-the-loop/on-the-loop), interface cues, escalation & fallback.
- **Human-machine teaming**
Align on Human-machine collaboration; roles and interactions between humans and machines, safety, security, reliability, trustworthiness considerations beyond conventional paradigms.
- **Sector packs**
Horizontal to sector tailoring; test methods & evidence tables reusable across domains Collaborate to explore sector-specific applications where both parties have activity.
- **Agentic AI**
Action items are defined to cover terminology, agent creation, management, operation and collaboration with multi agents, framework, interoperability, scheduling, and evaluation and measurement metrics, use cases. Although this item does not fall under the category of common items, given the rapid advancements in AI technology, it is recommended as a potential area for future collaboration.
- **Cross-over topics**
Identify cross-over topics between the six technology areas to be evaluated, particularly Cybersecurity/Privacy, Quantum, Data, but also with CEI and 5G/6G to be discussed.

Cloud/Edge/IoT Standardisation Priorities

- **Use Case and Requirement for CitiVerse**
Contribute to ITU-T SG20 Y.dtmv series with Korean use cases; collaborate with INSTAR on collecting more use cases from the European side working with relevant organizations (e.g. OASC).
- **Use Case and Requirements for Generative AI Service Enablement for IoT**
Define service requirements and use cases for Generative AIoT framework to jointly propose ITU-T SG20 or ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41.
- **Generative IoT Framework**
Align Korea's Generative AIoT initiatives with INSTAR's AIoT reference frameworks; develop concrete use cases with prototype implementations.

EU Cybersecurity/eID Standardisation Priorities

- **ISO 23042**
Development of the standard on decentralized identity systems.
- **JT013089**
Align on (Horizontal) Cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements Principles for cyber resilience (JTC13/WG9/PT1).
- **JT013090**
Align on (CRA) Horizontal standards for Generic Security Requirements Product (PT2).
- **JT013091**
Align on (CRA) Horizontal standards for vulnerability handling requirements (PT3).
- **ITU-T X.508 | ISO/IEC 9594-12**
Detailed description of cryptographic algorithm to be completed with detailed description of quantum-resistant algorithms, best practices for establishment of PKI, and mathematics behind cryptographic algorithms.
- **ITU-T X.509 | ISO/IEC 9594-8**
Basic standard for public-key infrastructure (PKI). Have migration capabilities for cryptographic algorithms. Plans for adding support for large scale IoT deployment.
- **ITU-T X.510 | ISO/IEC 9594-11**
Align on specification for secure protocols, tools for cryptographic algorithm migration and general migration techniques.
- **ITU-T X.dpki**
Replacing trust using trust anchors by having trust by consensus A step forward for European digital sovereignty. Specification for interworking among PKI domains and making certificate information globally available.
- **IEC 62351-90-4**
Align on migration of cryptographic algorithms for power systems.

Data Technologies Standardisation Priorities

- **Data Space Architecture: Reference architectures, personal data transfer (incl. Health data) and Internal governance, maturity models**
Contribute commonly to the International Dataspace Association (IDSA) and the prCEN/CLC/TS Maturity assessment of Common European Data Spaces.
- **Interoperability: Interoperability frameworks and Trusted transactions, cloud switching**
Contribute to the prCEN/TS Cloud Computing - Switching and Interoperability in a European context and prEN 18235-1-3 Trusted data transactions.
- **Semantic Standards: Trusted ontologies, Data Catalogue Vocabulary, Semantic assets and Graph data interfaces**
Contribute to ETSI Smart Applications REFERENCE Ontology (SAREF).
- **Trust and Data Governance: Governance frameworks, trust requirements and Identifiability, valuation, identifier structures**
Contribute commonly to forthcoming prEN on Quality assessment of internal data governance processes and Quality framework for internal data governance for participants in data spaces. Discuss possible common contributions to ongoing work in ISO TC 184 SC 4 Industrial Data.

Quantum Technologies Standardisation Priorities

- **Develop joint technical standards recognising EU & KR criteria for security assessment of QKD devices**
Draft and submit a liaison statement proposing a roadmap for harmonisation.
- **Align work between ETSI ISG QKD, ETSI TC CYBER & CEN-CENELEC JTC22 to support hybrid cryptographic approaches**
Submit a joint contribution to ISO/IEC JTC 3 Ad Hoc Group on Quantum Communication to advance hybrid QKD-PQC standardisation or establish cross-SDOs group for this purpose and work together.
- **Contribute joint use-case benchmark proposals to support application-oriented performance evaluation**
Provide joint contributions to ISO/IEC JTC 3 to: (i) propose application-oriented performance benchmarks across hardware platforms, and (ii) submit consolidated comments on layered model terminology to ensure consistency.
- **Explore applicability of AI in QKD networks (emerging topic)**
Organise joint testbeds to showcase how AI could be applied in QKD networks, referencing the 3800 TR developed by South Korea in ITU-T.

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Our consortium

Coordinator

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